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A RESEARCH OF THE USING PROCESSES OF AUTOMATIC COOKER AND STEAMERS IN TAIWAN

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ABSTRACT

Due to the progresses of living standards and medical technologies in recent years, people's life style has been changed gradually. Moreover, aging society indicates the issue of family structure changes such as decreasing number of family members and the growth of solitaries. In Taiwan, majority of people nowadays work under high pressure and demands. Eating, as one of physical factors, influences people's daily life. Electric cookers are the most common electric appliances in most families because their using process is easy and simple. However, their functions are not only cooking, but also are also steaming, stewing and braising food. They include the function of heating food up and keep food warm. As an efficient cooking design, electric cookers should be reviewed from the respective of user-centered design and safety.

The review aims to investigate the using process of electric cookers in Taiwan and the differences between variety of users, as well as the problems of using electrical cookers. There will be three stages contained at survey. Firstly, an interview will be regarding to designers' point of view, which refers the design strategies and thinkings that they have planned. Then, there will be another interview focusing on usage behaviors of electric cooker users. A half-open-questionnaire using at second stage will be based on the results of the first stage. Finally, verbal protocol analysis will be used to analyze all collected data.

Keywords: Electric Cookers, Universal design, User-centered

1. INTRODUCTION

With the development of the economy and technological progress with each passing day, the social lifestyle in Taiwan has gradually changed. Improvements in living standards and progress in medical technology have gradually extended the average life expectancy and transformed the population structure into an aging population. Population aging has become a general social phenomenon in advanced countries, and aging population will become an important component of population structure. According to the Japanese experience of an aging society, the mainstream design idea for small home appliances should be Universal Design (UD). Under the premise that it should be convenient for the elderly to use home appliances, the design of products that are more suitable for users will become an issue of high importance.

Food, clothing, housing, transportation, education, and entertainment are the six major essential elements of life, as well as the basic criteria for daily life. Because modern people lead busy lives, the eating pattern of simple and rapid cooking has developed, as have easy-to-use small home cooking appliances that simplify preparation work. The design of current small home cooking appliances is mainly based on meeting the needs of a population with a healthy physical status. However, such a design fails to meet users' diversified needs. Because home appliances are frequently used, it is easier to find users that are dissatisfied with them, as shown in Figure 1-1 [1]. Many home appliances cause dissatisfaction among users, owing to the addition of complicated operations and inexplicit labeling.

Therefore, it is necessary to re-examine the basic operations from a psychological aspect during usage.

Figure 1-1 Complicated operations is the factor leading to dissatisfaction with home appliances (Satoshi Nakagawa, 2008)

The service objects of products should be enlarged, and both healthy populations and disadvantaged groups should be taken into consideration. To respond to multiple needs and the corresponding safety, it is necessary to introduce the concept of universal design into home appliances to increase options for users. In addition, user-friendly home appliances should be designed to meet the needs of various groups. As eating habits in Taiwan are different from those in western cultures, the market share of steamers (Figure 1-2) [2] in Taiwan is higher than that in Europe and the United States. Although the import of electric rice cookers (Figure 1-3) [3] has increased the options for users, it is more convenient and simple to use steamers produced in Taiwan. Steamers are common cooking appliances that have been used in Taiwan for a long time. According to the annual report on industrial production statistics issued by the Department of Statistics of the Ministry of Economic Affairs Taiwan, the average market demand for steamers from 2000 to 2003 was approximately 610,000 units. Moreover, according to the survey data of the Taiwan Power Company, the penetration rate of steamers in 2003 was approximately 88.87% [4], showing a high penetration rate. In 2007, the sales volume of steamers increased 1.6 times [5]. Although steamers are a product with a high penetration rate, there has been no significant change in internal structures or type for years. Therefore, this research used the steamers frequently used in family in Taiwan as an example. Based on the concept of universal design, this study

probed into the current types of steamers, investigating if the usage status conformed to the spirit of general use and was accessible to different age groups. In addition, this study also investigated the difference between the usability and operation of current steamers, in order to resolve current shortcomings and find possible solutions. Based on the above, this research investigated if current steamers meet the concept and the application of universal design in order to understand the operational barriers and other difficulties experienced by different populations during the use of steamers, as well as to propose suggestions and improvement schemes.

Figure 1-2 steamers

Figure 1-3 electric rice cooker

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The investigation of this research was divided into two stages: interviews with designers and interviews with users. In terms of the preliminary investigation, because steamers are only a single product among numerous small home cooking appliances, during the interviews with designers, the main topic was small home cooking appliances. The correlation was further investigated based on designers' opinions on small home appliances, in order to further investigate the issues concerning the design and use of such small home appliances. During stage one, a total of five designers were interviewed. The designers' principles and opinions on the required basic components of small home appliances were obtained at this stage, and the small home appliances-related factors were summarized to conduct the next investigation.

During stage two, a total of ten users were interviewed. Relevant interview questions were developed according to the summarized results from the literature review and interviews with designers. The users were interviewed to obtain the problems they encountered during actual use. In addition, the verbal protocol analysis method was used to understand the problems, difficulties, and relevant

operational status experienced by users during the operation of steamers. This research further performed analyses based on the investigation of users' and designer's product-related opinions.

3. ANALYSIS ON THE INTERVIEW WITH DESIGNERS

Designers engaging in the design of small home cooking appliances were selected as the subjects of the interviews, and a total of five designers were interviewed. Of these, four were male and one was female. In-depth one-on-one interviews were conducted with five experienced designers of small home appliances, and the interviews were recorded on tape.

3.1 PRINCIPLES FOR DESIGNING SMALL HOME COOKING APPLIANCES

At this stage, the answers obtained from the interviews with the designers were arranged and analyzed to generalize the principles for designing small home appliances. Their design could be divided into the aspects of product type, design principle, operational interactive behavior and interface cognition. The principle for designing small home appliances were generalized into three aspects: the definition of types of small home cooking appliances, cognitive consideration of the design of small home cooking appliances, and the cognition and application of universal design.

The definition and types of small home cooking appliances:

Based on the interview data, the definition and types of small home cooking appliances provided by the subjects were discussed as follows. The subjects suggested that small home cooking appliances should be popular and have reasonable prices, as well as provide users with assistance in eating and usage to further improve their life quality. However, the most important essential element is safety. Small home cooking appliances are not designed according to specific types, and the products should be designed for different consumer groups.

According to the above findings, as a whole, small cooking appliances are general and popular products. Therefore, there is a need for them to possess characteristics such as convenience, functionality,

usability, and safety, to enable users to use them safely as well as improve life quality and convenience.

Cognitive Consideration for the design of product of small home cooking appliances:

- Restrictions and regulations on the design of small home cooking appliances

As a whole, product design is affected by restrictions on structure, materials, specifications and cost, and products should be produced that meet cost or market demand. The design principle should be put into practice in cost and marketing-based situations to find reasonable solutions. To meet the maximum need, there is a need to take design, market, and structure into consideration. It is necessary to formulate objectives for these needs and find corresponding solutions. Small home appliances themselves have to meet specific safety requirements. Therefore, it is necessary to develop safety mechanisms according to the characteristics and properties of the products to increase their usability.

- Interface cognition

The interface in use should vary with the user groups. The button pattern should be designed according to different properties and usages, and there is a need to consider and integrate the colors, letters, and button feedback. In terms of the elderly, it is necessary to consider their physical degeneration in order to design user-friendly interfaces. If the products generate heat, the operation interface should not be close to the heat source to prevent burns from occurring during operation. The presentation of the control panel requires complete design and arrangement. The images of the operational interface must have patterns and images that are comprehensible to the general public, and the labeling of buttons and images must be clear and understandable. With the development of microcomputer technology for products, more importance should be attached to the interface design, and logical consistency should also be applied to the operation of buttons. The prerequisite for interface design is the logicalness of the design, which should be user-friendly, followed by explicitness. Direct intuition should be applied to product design, which will make it more simple and

explicit for users to while using the product, such as the use of knobs in human machine interfaces.

- **Operational interaction between products and users**

The most important problem of small home cooking appliances is heat dissipation. If a product generates a higher temperature, there is a need to attach importance to safety. In terms of the aspect of the product itself, there is a need to inspect if its properties are risky. In general, small home appliances are usually powered by a power socket. Therefore, it is necessary to take the installation of safety devices and supporting measures into consideration. In terms of the usability, there is a need for users to understand how to use a product during operation, and the focus on the relationship between a product and its users should be on whether the operation is convenient. Product experimentation is one of the best approaches for understanding users' responses or procedures during operation. During the product experiment, a manufacturer can observe if the users operate products smoothly to verify their feedback response and immediately revise the design if needed.

Cognition and application of universal design:

- **General application of universal design**

The subjects of this research all understand the meaning and concept of universal design. The physical status of youth and the elderly may be different. Therefore, the original meaning of universal design is to provide disadvantaged groups with life care. In the beginning of product design, the concept of universal design can be introduced into the product. However, there is a need to conduct relevant assessments on the types and characteristics of the products to check if universal design is suitable for the products. Universal design is not the representative of an entire product, but a part of a product. Therefore, it is still necessary to consider different aspects of the product, such as safety, laws and regulations, and materials. The concept of universal design should be introduced into usability, since products are made to be operated and used. Consequently, there is a need to develop special design and assessment in this regard. A new idea and procedure should be

provided to enable universal design to be naturally integrated into products and environments according to differences in environment or need, in order to make products become more user-friendly.

- **The need for the introduction of universal design into small home cooking appliances**

Most small home cooking appliances generate heat; therefore, there is a need to consider product safety. It is necessary but not essential to introduce universal design into small home cooking appliances, because the corresponding design solutions for different types of small home appliances should be based on the assessment of their properties and needs. Occasionally, the compulsory introduction of the concept of universal design into a product will make a product lose other functions or usability. Therefore, the need of a product should be understood in advance, based on the concept of universal design, and universal design should be used to make a product become more humanized and user-friendly.

3.2 INVESTIGATION ON SMALL HOME COOKING APPLIANCES-RELATED FACTORS

Another major objective of the interviews with the designers was to summarize small home cooking appliances-related factors as the basis for the follow-up in-depth investigation. Consequently, the causes and essential factors concerning operational behavior were summarized from the answers of the subjects during the interview. The interview contents were summarized and arranged, and the factors were generalized into the following four aspects: operational interaction, interface design and feedback, operational cognition, and product image.

Operational interaction:

In terms of the correlation between the operational behavior of users and the usability of products, the interview contents showed that the integral consistency and smoothness in the operational behavior deserved investigation. The factors affecting subjects' operational interactions were summarized, including operational processes, time of use, user behavior, safety, behavioral response, operational consistency, and operational smoothness, among others.

Interface design and feedback:

In addition to the operational interactions, another important factor is the arrangement and design of the interface. To check if it is easy to operate an interface and if its feedback and design conform to operational modes (such as letter size, arrangement method, image, button feedback and hints), there is a need to use design to highlight its pattern. The use of interface design will make products become more user-friendly. The factors affecting subjects' responses to interface design and feedback summarized from the interview content included mode classification, button feedback, button type, letter size, color assortment, image, tactile sense, configuration, audio prompt, and visual sense, among others.

Operational cognition:

Product design should be user-centered. It is important to understand the responses reflected by users during operation. Manufacturers should discover the shortcomings or possible problems encountered by users during operation, to enable products to become more user-friendly for users. The factors affecting subjects' operational cognition, summarized from the interviews, included actual experiences, operational responses, operational habits, and expectations.

Product image:

The ultimate objective of the manufacture and production of products is to enable the consumer market to accept them. As a result, manufacturers expect to arouse consumers' attention to purchase products. The cognition and impression for the appearance of products can generate topics, and the focus may even be on the distinctive product image. The factors affecting subjects' product image, summarized from the interview, included arousing interest and attention, appearance, brand, function, style, and emotional projection.

3.3 SUMMARY

The analysis and integration of relevant literature and the interviews with designers showed that products are manufactured and designed for people to operate and use. Therefore, it is important to investigate if an interactive relationship between products and users has been developed to enable

users to use products safely. As a result, this research conducted a follow-up investigation on two major categories: the aspect of product operation and the aspect of internal perception.

In terms of product operation, it is necessary to consider if there is any safety mechanism to reduce or prevent the occurrence of risks. As for the operation, it is necessary to understand users' operational procedures and apply direct intuition to design products with logicalness and consistency. As for the design of the operational panel, it is necessary to consider button form, button size and feedback, interface location, images, letter size, chromaticity and contrast of colors for different groups. The operational interface should be simple and understandable; direct use is a more convenient operational mode for users.

Small home appliances are general and popular products with high usability, capacity, functionality, and safety for improving life quality, and are one of the main appliances assisting people in preparing food and eating. The orientation and function of products should be subject to differences in user groups, enabling users to operate products safely and conveniently, as well as create their use value. Therefore, small home appliances were generalized into the two major categories of product operation and internal perception for investigation. Two classifications, operational interaction and interface design and feedback referred to the usage and participation of the products themselves, covering whether the operational behavior and mode of the products were correct, and thus they were classified into the aspect of product operation. Two classifications, operational cognition and product image, covered the users' internal perception process to further generate various emotional cognitions and response linkages, and they were thus classified into the aspect of internal perception. The relevant factors mentioned above and their corresponding relationships were compared and summarized in Table 3-1 as the basis for the follow-up analysis on the interviews with users.

Categories	Classifications	Factors
Product operation	Operational interaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> operational procedure usage time user behavior, safety behavioral participation operational consistency operational smoothness
	Interface design and feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> classification of modes button feedback button type letter size color assortment images tactile sense configuration audio prompts visual sense
Internal perception	Operational cognition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> actual experience operational response operational habit expectation
	Product image	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> arousing interest arousing attention appearance brand function style emotional projection

Table 3-1 Classification of various factors

4. INTERVIEWS WITH USERS

Users who had operated steamers and were willing to receive and cooperate with the interview were selected as the subjects, and a total of ten users were interviewed. Of these, two were male and eight were female. As for the age distribution, the subjects were distributed at all ages. All of the

subjects had steamers at home. As for frequency of use, four of the subjects used steamers daily, one used them occasionally, one used them frequently, and four of them used steamers several times weekly. As for occupations, one subject was a student, two subjects were single office workers, three were both housewives and office workers, one was an office worker, and three of the subjects were housewives. More effective investigational results were obtained through the interviews with the users. The data are summarized in Table 4-1.

Subject	Sex	Age	Possessing steamers or not	Frequency of use of steamers	Occupation
A	F	23	Y	Daily	Student
B	M	26	Y	Frequently	Single office worker
C	F	30	Y	Several time weekly	Single office worker
D	F	40	Y	Several time weekly	Housewife and office worker
E	M	40	Y	Daily	Office worker
F	F	43	Y	Several time weekly	Housewife and office worker
G	F	43	Y	Several time weekly	Housewife and office worker
H	F	60	Y	Daily	Housewife
I	F	70	Y	Occasionally	Housewife
J	F	83	Y	Daily	Housewife

Table 4-1 Basic information of the interviewed users

4.1 DISCUSSION ON THE ENCODING RESULTS OF THE VERBAL PROTOCOL ANALYSIS METHOD

The verbal protocol analysis method was used to compare the encoding results, and relevant categories and classification factors were summarized according to the interviews with the designers. According to the interviews, four classifications (operational interaction, interface design and feedback, operational cognition, and product image) were obtained and encoded for discussion and analysis to further find the problems experienced by the subjects during usage. The

explanations about two aspects, the results of the discussion on encoding and the investigation of the use of steamers were given as follows:

The verbal data were encoded according to the previously established encoding system, and the results obtained were described as follows. The total number of punctuated sentences of each classification was compared with one another. Table 4-2 summarizes the number of punctuated sentences for each subject. The number of punctuated sentences for each subject was totaled up and was compared with one another according to its classification. The data revealed that the total numbers of punctuated sentences for operational interaction and operational cognition were larger, (151 sentences and 135 sentences, respectively). There were 30 punctuated sentences for interface design and feedback. The number of punctuated sentences for product image was smaller (26 sentences). This was a significant difference, suggesting that in terms of the operation of steamers, users encountered more problems in the aspect of operational interaction. As for the design interface and feedback, because the interface pattern of steamers was simpler, with a single function and less complexity, users encountered fewer problems with the interface design and feedback. As for the aspect of product image, users suggested that the appearance of steamers had never changed significantly and they mainly purchased it for the need of convenience. Most of the users were satisfied with the current status and had fewer questions about product image.

	Product operation		Internal perception	
	Operational interaction	Interface design and feedback	Operational cognition	Product image
A	28	6	28	4
B	18	2	16	3
C	18	2	14	1
D	13	4	11	4
E	14	2	12	3
F	15	1	12	3
G	10	2	11	4
H	14	6	13	2
I	6	2	5	1
J	15	3	13	1
Sum	151	30	135	26
Total	181		161	

Table 4-2 Comparison on the total number of encoded punctuated sentences in the interviews with users

4.2 INVESTIGATION ON THE USE OF STEAMERS

After relevant classifications and factors were obtained from the interviews with the designers, the factors were divided into two major categories: the aspect of product operation and the aspect of internal perception. The aspect of product operation could be further divided into the two classifications of operational interaction and interface design and feedback, and internal perception could be further divided into the two classifications of operational cognition and product image. Therefore, the interview contents of the users were divided into the following four classifications of operational interaction, interface design and feedback, operational cognition, and product image

Operational interaction:

Steamers are usually used for steaming, cooking and stewing, and are seldom used for pan-frying or stir-frying. Users suggested that the operational procedures of steamers were simple and comprehensible, and they only needed to press the button to complete the cooking function. Therefore, steamers were cooking appliances that could be conveniently operated. As for the control of the water volume in the outer pot, users still failed to add adequate volume of water. They would regularly wash the steamers, and it was very easy to clean the one-body formed appearance. They would clean steamers by wiping them. Because steamers were

frequently used appliances, they were mainly fixed at the top of a table or cabinet and were seldom moved or stored. However, a clamp had to be purchased additionally. Therefore, most users would directly use thick cloths to pick up the inner pot. During the use of steamers, steam is generated. After opening the lid, most users would wait for a while to take out the food to prevent themselves from being burnt by steam or the overheated pot.

Interface design and feedback:

The interface design and mode classification of steamers were quite simple and there were no excessive images or letters. The users only had to press a single button to start cooking and the added left-right toggle button was for thermal insulation only. The interface pattern was simple and comprehensible. Therefore, the users suggested that they were easy to operate and understand. When they pressed the button to start cooking, a feedback signal would show on the interface device, representing that the steamers were in use. After cooking was completed, the internal automatic power off device would be triggered when the water had dried out. The light would go out and the button would jump up to reduce the occurrence of risks. Audio feedback would also occur.

Operational cognition:

The users found it easy and safe to operate steamers. In addition, the operational pattern of steamers was mainly stable, and users were satisfied with maintenance of the status quo. As for the movement to take out the food, they suggested that it was inconvenient to take it out because the pot was placed at the bottom. It was uneasy for the users to take out the pot and they would easily spill out the food or liquid. Moreover, because the internal space was small, users could easily get burnt by the internal wall. They could not control the water volume and evaluated the volume based on their feelings and experiences, which could easily lead to excessive power waste or incompletely cooked food. Therefore, they often had to re-open the pot lid to add water for usage. When the food they took out was overweight, the clamp might easily slide off, and thus it was difficult to use properly. During the use of steamers, a large amount of steam would be

generated. Because the users had no idea what the temperature was, they could easily get burnt and they were also afraid of being burnt by steam when opening the pot lid.

Product Image:

Because it is simple and convenient to operate steamers, users mainly consider convenience and usability when purchasing them. The users suggested that novelty and strong functions were not the essential properties of steamers. Their impression of steamers was more traditional, and they suggested that the functions of steamers should focus on high convenience and usability. They attached importance to the selection of brands and suggested that the quality of famous brands would be guaranteed. They would determine the size of steamers according to their needs or the number of family members. The high durability of steamers was also one of the reasons for purchase, followed by color and appearance.

5. CONCLUSIONS

After performing the inductive analysis, this study found that the simple pattern and operational interface of steamers made them easy and convenient to use. However, the difficulties experienced during the operation of steamers still needed to be reduced. This research summarized four major difficulties as follows: the water volume cannot be assessed accurately, it is difficult to take out the pot, steam problems, and visual cognition.

The water volume cannot be assessed accurately:

The water volume of the outer pot cannot be assessed accurately, which may lead to excessive power waste and incompletely cooked food. In addition, users may be perplexed because they have to re-open the lid to add water.

It is uneasy to take out the pot:

The pot clamp has to be purchased separately and is inconvenient to use, owing to differences in the size of steamers. For example, if the cooked food is overweight, it will be difficult to clamp onto the pot because the clamp may easily slide off. Therefore, most users elect to use thick cloths to pick up the inner pot. As the pot is usually placed at the bottom

of steamers, it is inconvenient to take food out, and food or liquids may easily spill out.

Steam problems:

After the cooking is completed, users will be nervous about being burnt by a large amount of steam when they open the lid. They will also be afraid of getting burnt by the internal wall. Because heat will be generated after cooking is completed and the temperature of the outer pot will also increase, if users are not reminded or informed of such information by a feedback signal, they could easily get burnt.

Visual cognition:

The button of the operational interface is at the lower part of steamers, and the interface pattern is not always obvious. Therefore, in terms of visual cognition, it is harder for the elderly to clearly identify it.

After the users' interview contents were divided into the four major classifications of operational interaction, interface design and feedback, operational cognition, and product image, information on operation-related behaviors and specific problems regarding steamers were obtained. The shortcomings to be improved were discussed and suggestions were provided, as shown in Table 5-1.

Classifications	Analysis on the results of the use of steamers	Suggestions for improvement
Operational interaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generally have a complete safety mechanism. • It is easy and convenient to operate and use it 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the safety mechanism is necessary • the operation should be simple and user-friendly.
Interface design and feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is simple and easy to operate the interface. • There is a visual feedback signal and audio feedback on the interface button. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •The interface design should be as identifiable and usable as possible. •The feedback will enable users to clearly understand the information.
Operational cognition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is convenient, simple and safe to operate it. • It is inconvenient to take out the food because the space is too small and it is easy to get burnt. • Water volume cannot be controlled. • Users are afraid of being burnt by the pot lid or steam. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •The size of internal space of steamers can be changed to reduce the chance of being burnt. •There should be a note or reminder to enable the users to control the water volume in the outer pot.
Product image	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tradition and durability. • Convenience for use. • Attaching importance to brands. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is necessary for the products to possess functions and convenience. Even though it is simple.

Table 5-1 Summary of the results of user operation of steamers and suggestions for improvement

Based on the analyses of the interviews, this research found that the use of the product was correlated with user interactions. As a whole, the interaction between products and users should be consistent and accurate, to enable users to easily understand and operate the interface. The operational interface or the interface pattern and arrangement must be comprehensible and simple, and it is preferable to operate the interface through intuitive responses to enable users to use products safely and without feeling confused. The products themselves should be changed according to different needs, such as the needs for usability, capacity, functionality, and safety.

After the foresaid interviews with designers and users were conducted, this research obtained the information on operational status and problems encountered by users during the operation of steamers, which is beneficial to the understanding of the actual operational situation of steamers and makes it more convenient for users to operate them. Moreover, this research also found that the use of steamers could be investigated from the four aspects of operational interaction, interface design and feedback, operational cognition, and product image, respectively. The summarized difficulties may be further analyzed and discussed in follow-up studies. According to the generalization, the required relevance principles for the operation of steamers are safety, operability and feedback property.

Safety:

Steamers are plug-in home appliances. It is necessary for them to possess a complete safety mechanism

and protection mechanism to prevent dangers from occurring and to enable users to operate them safely. In addition, because they have a built-in fault tolerance design, accidents should not occur, even when used incorrectly.

Operationality:

The operation has to be simple and comprehensible to users, to stop them from feeling confused during usage and completely understand the operational procedures.

Feedback property:

The interface design must be identifiable and user-friendly. In addition, there should be a feedback signal to inform users of specific information more explicitly, such as visual or aural feedback signals

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